

REACTION HARDENING OF TiO₂/AL ALLOYS COMPOSITES STIMULATED BY DOPING

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SUMMARY: The reactivities of rutile type TiO₂/Al composites have been investigated for the purpose of defining the effects of some impurities in rutile type TiO₂ on the solid state reaction. Because such reaction in the composites is induced by impurity in reinforcement and is considered practically valuable. The reactivities of each TiO₂/Al composites, which are fabricated from pure Al and TiO₂ doped with alkali and alkali earth metal oxides respectively, have been examined by DSC. Doped Na, K, Rb and Cs except for Li caused the TiO₂/Al composites to react on the solid state. Otherwise, in the case of alkali earth metals, doped Ca, Sr and Ba except for Be and Mg effects on the reaction of the composites on the solid state. These results indicate that some elements which are large ionic radius, caused the reaction of the composites on the solid state. In addition, it is seemed that the exothermic reaction of the composites on the solid state is larger with increasing ionic radius of the dopants. These results reveal the possibility of reaction control between matrix alloy and reinforcement by doping. In other words, it is shown that new flexible MMC and the process, which harden by heat treatment are produced.

KEYWORDS: TiO₂, Al alloys, Metal matrix composites, Heat treatment, Reaction, Hardening, Doping, Al₂O₃, Al-Ti intermetallic

INTRODUCTION

Much attention on metal matrix composites has been recently paid to take advantage of the reaction between matrix alloy and reinforcement. The reaction has great potential to offer economically high performance composites. From the views, various kinds of fabrication procedure for the composites have been developed. They are divided into classes by the reactants states, e.g. liquid-liquid, liquid-solid, solid-solid and gas-liquid, and therefore, have various features. Some of them are practically applying for machine components, but a disadvantage of these composites is lower machinability. Because, most of these composites have been fabricated accompanying with the reaction, and resulting to include reaction products in it.

In the previous conferences, we have been proposed new composites which harden by heat treatment on the solid phase after they are fabricated by conventional squeeze casting[1]. In rutile type TiO_2/Al alloys system, three kinds composites had been obtained by squeeze casting due to the reactivity between reinforcement and matrix[2]. One of them is plain composites which particulate rutile type TiO_2 merely dispersed in Al alloys. It had been found that the composites hardened not only on the liquid phase, but also on the solid phase, and shown the commercial significance of the composites availed the reaction on solid phase, such as behavior of the hardenability, effects of alloy elements and some properties[3,4]. Furthermore, it has been found that the reaction of TiO_2/Al composites on the solid state is stimulated by a impurity in TiO_2 , which is Na[5]. In this work, the reactivities between TiO_2 and Al composites were investigated to research of the reaction mechanism and other effective elements as dopants.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Fabrication of TiO_2/Al composites

High purity rutile type TiO_2 (Wako Chem. Co., 99.9%) powder and Al(99.99%) were employed as reinforcement or matrix respectively. Chemical compositions of impurities in the TiO_2 are shown in Table 1. The particulate TiO_2 is very fine powder which the mean diameter is about $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig.1). For doping to reinforcement, alkali or alkali earth metal elements, which are Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs and Be, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, were added respectively to the TiO_2 powder as each element's oxide or carbonate. These employed additives are first grade reagents. Amount of each additive is slightly 0.3 mass% as each element's oxide, respectively. The TiO_2 powder was mixed with each additives by planetary ball mill. The each mixed TiO_2 powder was formed by cold press(0.3MPa) in die, and the shaped TiO_2 block($20 \times 50 \times \sim 17\text{mm}$) was fired at 1273 ~ 1473K. As some kinds of dopants to TiO_2 cause large shrinkage during sintering, the firing temperature was changed as being almost same Vf of reinforcement. Thus, the fabricated TiO_2 block as preform has 32.5 ~ 40.3% as volume fraction of TiO_2 and was located in the casting

Table 1: Impurity elements in high purity TiO_2 powder(99.9 mass%)

(mass ppm)

Al	Zn	Na	K	Ca	Fe	Ta	Cr	Ni	As	Pb	Mg	Ba
25.0	1.5	7.8	0.3	8.0	13.8	28.2	12.3	4.3	4.7	1.8	1.9	0.3

die. Subsequently, the composites were fabricated by squeeze casting under lower temperature condition. That is, preheating temperature of the preform and the die were less than 523K and pouring temperature of melt is less than 973K. Thus fabricated TiO_2/Al composites has not hardly reacted.

Fig 1: Particle size distribution and SEM image of rutile type high purity TiO_2 powder

Some Examination on Reactivity of the Composites

The specimens for thermal analysis are cut out from each composites and examined the reactivity on the solid state by DSC. The structures of each composites corresponding to proceeding of reaction were observed and analyzed by SEM-EDX, TEM-EDX and XRD. From the view of reaction mechanism, the amount of element Na was analyzed before and after dissolving case of TiO_2 by fluorescent X ray analysis. Fluoride solution was used as dissolving fluid The microstructure of TiO_2 observed by TEM from the view of seeing effect of the additives.

Furthermore, the interface between sintered TiO_2 and pure Al was examined with regard to interaction between reinforcement and matrix.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reactivities and Structures of the Doped TiO_2/Al Composites

DSC thermograms of each TiO_2/Al composites doped with alkali metal which is univalent are shown in Fig.2. The curves of Li_2O doped TiO_2/Al composites did not react on the solid state (arrow a). But, when Na_2O or K_2O doped TiO_2 , it shows that the composites indicate little peak on the solid state (arrow a) due to exothermic reaction. Then, in the case of Rb_2O , the peak is more define at the same temperature. Furthermore, Cs_2O doped TiO_2/Al composites reveal more greater peak. On the other hand, in the case of alkali earth metal elements which are divalent, DSC thermograms of each doped TiO_2/Al composites are shown in Fig.3. Although the curves of BeO or MgO doped TiO_2/Al composites did not react on the solid state (arrow a), one of CaO doped TiO_2/Al composites emerged little peak of exothermic reaction at the same temperature. When SrO doped TiO_2 , the composites appear sharp peak.

Then BaO doped TiO_2 , the composites show more large peak. From the results of Fig.2 and 3, the later element of atomic number on periodic table give rise to larger peak 'a' versus 'c' for exothermic reaction in each figure respectively. The tendency also corresponds to the order of ionic radius of each element.

Fig. 2: DSC thermograms of TiO_2/Al composites doped with 0.3 mass% of alkali metal oxides.

Fig. 3: DSC thermograms of TiO_2/Al composites doped with 0.3 mass% of alkali earth metal oxides.

For representative examples, XRD of BeO or Rb₂O doped TiO₂/Al composites after heat treatment on the solid state are shown in Fig.4. In the case of BeO, the XRD patterns does not change before and after heat treatment. However, in the case of Rb₂O, the main peak of Al₃Ti near one of Al appears after heat treatment on the XRD patterns. The Rb₂O doped TiO₂/Al composites actually hardened after heat treatment. Thus, TiO₂/Al composites proceed the reaction by heat treatment on the solid state.

Fig. 4: XRD patterns of TiO₂/Al composites doped with small amount of BeO or Rb₂O before and after heat treatment. reaction by heat treatment on the solid state.

Fig.5 shows TEM structures and point analysis of Na₂O doped TiO₂/Al composites during reaction hardening. Point a or b in Al matrix contains small amount of Ti and O. Point c or d is thought to be in TiO₂ particle region. Al is slightly detected at point c and is considerably detected at point d. Al-Ti intermetallic may be produced at point d. In this way, every TiO₂ in the composites during reaction hardening contains somewhat Al. Therefore, it is thought that Al diffuses into TiO₂ comparatively. Since then, it is also revealed there is difference of proceeding of the reactions between each TiO₂ particles and matrix in the composites.

For the purpose of confirming the morphology of the reaction, SEM structures in TiO₂/Al composites during reaction hardening were observed (shown in Fig.6). When the reaction of the composites begin from (a) to (b), white crusty layer precipitates surround TiO₂ particle, and the layer thickness increases with time such as (c), (c'). The white layer is α-Al₂O₃ certainly from the results of XRD. But, the crusty α-Al₂O₃ did not develop into the core of TiO₂ particle, and the core seemed to be Al-Ti intermetallic.

Fig. 5: Microstructure and point analysis at the respective locations of TiO_2/Al composites on the way of reaction hardening by TEM-EDX.

Fig. 6: SEM structures of practical grade TiO_2/Al composites. (a)As cast, (b)873K-10min, (c)873K-60min, (c')Magnified of (c).

Effects of Doping Element on Interaction

Interface constituted of sintered high purity TiO_2 or practical TiO_2 contained Na as impurity and Al was fabricated by squeeze casting, and the comparison of both interfaces after heat treatment on the solid state is shown in Fig.7. In the case of Na contained TiO_2 , TiO_2 side changes dark layer near the interface after heat treatment, though the interface does not change in the case of high purity TiO_2 . Fig. 8 shows XRD of the dark layer. The color changed dark layer is almost rutile type TiO_2 from the results. It is recognized that the dark

layer have electric conductivity too. Considering these results, it can be fairly certain that the dark layer is produced to be removed oxygen from TiO_2 . That is, TiO_2 has been partially reduced by Al. From these phenomena, it is indicated that either oxygen is easy to move in TiO_2 or Al is easy to diffuse into TiO_2 when TiO_2 contain a specific element such as Na.

Fig. 7: Optical microstructures of interface between Al and sintered TiO_2 before and after heat treatment. (a) Practical grade TiO_2 - as cast, (a') Practical grade TiO_2 - after heat treatment (873K-120h), (b) High purity TiO_2 - as cast, (b') High purity TiO_2 - after heat treatment (873K-120h).

Fig. 8: XRD patterns of the dark layer of sintered practical grade TiO_2 bonded with Al after heat treatment.

Anyway, it is significant to find out where such specific element is located in TiO₂ from the view of reaction mechanism. When each specific element in Fig.2 and 3 doped TiO₂, Lattice parameter of TiO₂ was attempted to get by XRD. But the results corresponding to ionic radius of each element were not obtained. Table 2 shows the concentrations of case and core of TiO₂ particles which were doped with Na₂O. From the results, it is clear that Na exists near surface of TiO₂ particle. This can be extended in the case of alkali or alkali earth metal element from the phase diagrams.

Table 2: Analysis of impurity oxide of case and core in TiO₂ particle.

Sample	Impurity oxide	Whole particle	After dissolution	Case (difference)
Doped TiO ₂	Na ₂ O	0.028	0.000	0.028

(mass%)

Reaction Mechanism

It has been reconfirmed that the high purity TiO₂ hardly react with Al by heat treatment on the solid state and specific element doped TiO₂ reacts. The reaction represents as follows equation from reaction products.

In equation (1), the change of freedom energy ' ΔG ' gives negative ($\approx -173\text{kJ/mol}$) on the solid state ($\sim 873\text{K}$). Therefore, The reaction of equation (1) has to proceed, but not proceed actually (in the case of high purity TiO₂). However, it has been apparent when alkali or alkali earth metal element except for a part of them dopes into TiO₂, the reaction of the composite comes to proceed.

We shall discuss the reaction mechanism between specific element contained TiO₂ and Al on the solid state. In the high purity TiO₂/Al composites, the reaction occurred firstly at the interface, and does not almost proceed since. It was observed in the composites that Al₂O₃ is thin produced at the interface and Al-Ti intermetallic existed massively near the interface. The first reaction on the interface makes Al₂O₃. As the heat treatment is carried out on the solid state, Al or Ti have to diffuse through the Al₂O₃ so as to continue the reaction. It was reported that Ti could diffuse fast in Al₂O₃ relatively[6]. But, the self diffusion of Al in Al₂O₃ is extremely late at same temperature[7]. Accordingly, it is considered that the late diffusion retard the reaction between TiO₂ and Al.

However, when alkali or alkali earth metal element dopes TiO₂, it is predicted that oxide complex is produced to react with TiO₂ at surface, partially or overall. In fact, when the amount of dopant which is Na or Ba increased over 1 mass%, Na₂Ti₆O₁₃ or Ba₂Ti₉O₂₀ was detected by XRD, respectively. Thus, these oxide complexes could be also produced in relation to another dopants from phase diagram. Then the ion radius of the elements accelerated the reaction are large ($\geq 1\text{\AA}$) except for some dopants. Considering that these

dopants form substitutional solid solutions with TiO_2 is impossible, because cation radius which can be substituted for Ti ion limits to its 15% increment. Then, such large space does not indeed exist in interstitial of rutile structure in TiO_2 . Accordingly, The dopants accelerated the reaction can not consider to diffuse into TiO_2 particle. From these results, it is thought that alkali or alkali earth metal elements form thin film of oxide complex with TiO_2 at interface except for Li, Be, Mg.

These oxide complex constituted of each alkali or alkali earth metal element and TiO_2 is known to have a layer or tunnel structure. These cation are sited in interlayer or tunnel of the structures and can be easy to exchange another alkali or alkali earth metal cation. The oxide complexes react with Al furthermore, and ternary oxide complexes may be produced. The ternary oxide complexes have occasionally one dimensional ion conductor or super ion conductor, etc.[8]. Anyhow Al ion is thought to diffuse through such as the complex oxide easily.

Fig.9 shows schematic illustration of reaction mechanism. As above mentioned, in alkali or alkali earth metal element doped TiO_2/Al composites, the oxide complex layer which constituted of alkali or alkali earth metal element and Al, is produced partially on the TiO_2 . In site of direct contact interface between TiO_2 and Al, matrix Al reacts with TiO_2 to form Al_2O_3 as initial reaction by heat treatment on the solid state. In the site of oxide complex layer on the TiO_2 , matrix Al changes to Al ion to release electric charges on the interface. The Al ion diffuses fast through the complex oxide compared with through α - Al_2O_3 by the heat treatment and therefore, Al ion can attain to TiO_2 . Rutile structure of TiO_2 is known to have diffusion path in the direction of c axis. It had been reported that the diffusion rate of Li ion in the direction of c axis of rutile has 108 times compared with a or b axis[9]. It had been also reported that thus strong anisotropy of impurity diffusion in rutile had not only univalent ion such as Li, but also divalent or trivalent ion such as B, O, Ni, Co, Fe, Cr[10-13]. From the facts, Al ion (0.53 Å) which is smaller ion radius than one of Li (0.74 Å), is considered to diffuse to inner of TiO_2 . The maximum radius of void in rutile structure is reported as 0.77 Å by Wittke[10]. Diffused Al ion in TiO_2 reacts with O ion to form Al_2O_3 and to dissociate into Ti ion. For the development of the produced Al_2O_3 , O ions have to diffuse in TiO_2 . But O ions are difficult to diffuse because of the large ionic radius. Therefore, the growth of Al_2O_3 is so late, Al ions diffuse to inner of TiO_2 to nucleate and grow of Al_2O_3 . Then the dark layer observed in Fig.7 shows that TiO_2 is reduced partially. The apparatus activation energy is calculated 255.1 kJ/mol from DSC to use Augis and Bennet's method[14].

Fig. 9: Schematic illustrations of promoted reaction mechanism by impurity elements in TiO_2/Al composites.

As the value is closest to one of O ion in rutile type TiO_2 [15], the reaction of TiO_2/Al composites on the solid state is considered to be controlled by the diffusion of O ion in TiO_2 .

On the other hand, as the dissociated Ti ion is easy to diffuse through Al_2O_3 , Ti ion received electric charge released from Al to form metal Ti on the interface. The Ti immediately dissolved in Al. Al-Ti intermetallic is produced because Ti is so late to diffuse in Al[16]. Thus Al-Ti intermetallic increases with proceeding the reaction and comes to occupy in matrix.

The following reactions proceed on the both interfaces.

On the interface of Al / oxide complex;

On the interface of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 / \text{TiO}_2$;

The doping of Li, Be or Mg oxide to TiO_2 gives no effect on the solid reaction of TiO_2/Al composites. The ionic radius of Li, Be or Mg are 0.74 Å, 0.35 Å, 0.72 Å respectively and as above mentioned, the radius of the diffusion path in the direction of c axis of rutile is 0.77 Å. Therefore, when TiO_2 doped with each oxide of Li, Be or Mg was fired at 1273~1473K, the each ion is presumed to diffuse into TiO_2 through c axis of rutile structure. As a consequence, the oxide complex of the each elements and TiO_2 could not produced. The ionic radius of Na or Ca are 1.00 Å or 1.02 Å which are larger radius than 15% increment of 0.77 Å. Indeed, the another ions of alkali or alkali earth metal have larger radius with later elements in periodical table and oxide complex is produced.

Furthermore, it is thought that the magnitude of exothermic reaction on the composites on the solid state depends on volume diffusivities of Al ion in the oxide complex. When large ion sites in interlayer or tunnel of oxide complex, the interlayer or the tunnel is broadened and Ti-O6 octahedron may be distorted to widen the lattice. Anyhow, Al ion is easy to pass through the oxide complex with larger ion sited in the interlayer or the tunnel.

Rutile type TiO_2/Al composites can harden by heat treatment on the solid state, which contained the specific elements in reinforcement. The reaction hardening is considered effects of ion diffusivity due to the oxide complex, their's structures and rutile structure.

CONCLUSION

In the reaction hardening of rutile type TiO_2/Al composites on the solid state, the reactivity of the composites in which each oxide of alkali or alkali earth metal elements was doped to TiO_2 , was examined and the reaction mechanism was investigated. These results as follows;

- (1) TiO_2/Al composites shows exothermic reaction on the solid state which Na, K, Rb, Cs, Ca, Sr, Ba doped in the reinforcement except for Li, Be, Mg.
- (2) The exothermic reaction of the composites on the solid state appeared to be intensive with increasing ionic radius of the dopants.

- (3) The reaction mechanism of the composites on the solid state can be explained by the formation of titanate alkali or alkali earth metal oxide, their structures, the rutile structure and the diffusivity of each ion.

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